

Marginal lands for Growing Industrial Crops

D7.3 – Key findings and transferability

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Type

- R** Document, report
- DEM** Demonstrator, pilot, prototype
- DEC** Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.
- OTHER**

Dissemination Level

- PU** Public
- CO** Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Publishable executive summary

Low input cultivation of industrial crops in land with biophysical marginality can provide valuable resources for biobased products and bioenergy.

Important marginality challenges that were improved with the cultivation of industrial crops in marginal land in the understudy Good Practice case studies include among others shallow soil depth, low fertility and light sandy soils, soil contamination, low water availability, limiting rooting conditions and steep slopes.

The work in this report discusses the key findings for the characteristics of the selected industrial crops and the marginality challenges improved with their cultivation. Following it discusses the level of potential transferability for the lessons learnt per key attribute (biophysical- environmental, economic, and social) and development stage to other European regions.

1 Introduction

Low input cultivation of industrial crops can provide valuable resources for high added value biobased products and bioenergy. Research in the Magic project analysed the sustainable development of resource-efficient and economically profitable industrial crops grown on land with biophysical marginality across Europe.

The work in this task summarises the findings from the Deliverable 7.1 Good Practices and Deliverable 7.2 Analysis of Good Practices, literature review, stakeholder interviews and consultations with regional actors.

It discusses the key characteristics of the selected industrial crops, the marginality challenges improved with their cultivation as well as the lessons learnt and transferability for the key biophysical- environmental, economic and social attributes.

The outputs from this analysis can inform recommendations for other regions and have provided input to the policy recommendations in Task 7.4 (Deliverable 7.5).

2 Challenges that Magic and Good Practice case studies address

Research in Magic combined field trials, land use modelling, integrated sustainability assessment and participatory approaches to provide evidence on:

- how much and what type of land can be categorised as marginal in Europe, and
- which crop species are or can be adapted to European agro-climatic zones and facilitate overcoming land marginality whilst providing raw materials for the biobased economy.

The work in Work Package 7 focused on identifying and analysing a set of Good Practice cases that cultivate industrial crops in European regions to restore marginal land. Figure 1 presents key facts from the European Environment Agency (EEA) for the main marginality challenges addressed.

Figure 1 Marginality challenges addressed by the Good Practice cases in Magic

A brief outline of the main issues is presented below to contextualise the analysis in this report. Detailed information can be found in the following Magic Deliverables:

- Elbersen, B., Van Eupen, M., Verzandvoort, S., Boogaard, H., Mucher, S., Cicarrel, T., Elbersen, W., Mantel, S., Bai, Z., McCallum, I., Iqbal, Y., Lewandowski, I., Von Cossel, M., Carrasco, J., Ramos, C.C., Sanz, M., Ciria Ciria, P., Monti, A., Consentoni, S., Scordia, D., Eleftheriadis, I., 2018a. Deliverable 2.6. Methodological approaches to identify and map marginal land suitable for industrial crops in Europe WUR, Wageningen, Netherlands. In:

MAGIC project reports, supported by the EU's Horizon 2020 programme under GA No. 727698, CRES, Greece. <http://magic-h2020.eu/documents-reports/>

- Elbersen, B., Van Verzandvoort, M., Boogaard, S., Mucher, S., Cicarelli, T., Elbersen, W., Mantel, S., Bai, Z., McCallum, I., Iqbal, Y., Lewandowski, I., Von Cossel, M., Carrasco, J., Ramos, C.C., Sanz, M., Ciria, P., Monti, A., Consentino, S., Scordia, D., Eleftheriadis, I., 2018b. Deliverable 2.1. Definition and classification of marginal lands suitable for industrial crops in Europe. In: MAGIC project reports, supported by the EU's Horizon 2020 programme under GA No. 727698, CRES, Greece. <http://magic-h2020.eu/documents-reports/>
- von Cossel, M., Iqbal, Y., Scordia, D., Cosentino, S. L., Elbersen, B., Staritsky, I., van Eupen, M., Mantel, S., Prysiazhniuk, O., Maliarenko, O., Lewandowski, I. (2018): Low-input agricultural practices for industrial crops on marginal land (Deliverable D4.1). In: MAGIC project reports, supported by the EU's Horizon 2020 programme under GA No. 727698, University of Hohenheim, Stuttgart (Hohenheim), Germany. <http://magic-h2020.eu/documents-reports/>

2.1 Soil carbon

According to the European Environment Agency and the European Climate Adaptation Platform Climate-ADAPT¹:

- Soil carbon stocks in the EU-27 are around 75 billion tonnes of carbon; around 50 % of which is located in Ireland, Finland, Sweden and the United Kingdom (because of the large area of peatlands in these countries).
- The largest emissions of CO₂ from soils are due to conversion (drainage) of organic soils, and amount to 20–40 tonnes of CO₂ per hectare per year.

The most effective option to manage soil carbon in order to mitigate climate change is to preserve existing stocks in soils, and especially the large stocks in peat and other soils with a high content of organic carbon. Another option, adopted in the Good Practice cases in Magic, is the cultivation of perennial lignocellulosic crops that can foster the increased return of organic matter, lead to sequestration of soil carbon and improvements in soil fertility (van Cossel, et al. 2020).

2.2 Soil contamination

Municipal and industrial waste disposal and treatment causes around a third of Europe's soil contamination problem. Metal industries and petrol stations are also common sources of soil contamination, while mining is an important source in some countries². Traditional remediation involves excavating the contaminated soil and disposing of it in another location.

Another option is phytoremediation. Phytoremediation can be a successful strategy to be used in those cases where the pressure on land to be used for other purposes or pollution levels are low to moderate but still in excess of for example agricultural advisory levels³. In addition, rather than aiming to clean the soil, crops grown on moderately or highly polluted soils also

¹ <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/about>

² Payá Pérez Ana and Rodríguez Eugenio Natalia (2018), Status of local soil contamination in Europe: Revision of the indicator "Progress in the management Contaminated Sites in Europe, EUR 29124 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2018, ISBN 978-92-79-80072-6, doi:10.2760/093804, JRC107508

³ Liederkerke, M van; Masson, J.; Perez, A.P.; Jones, A.; Geissen, V.; Baritz, R.; Havlicek, E; Silva, V.; Yang, X.. Regional status of soil pollution: Europe. Global Symposium on soil pollution Rome, Italy 2-4 May 2018 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327981472_Regional_status_of_soil_pollution_Europe

can prevent deleterious effects of the pollutants present on nearby water systems or humans living in the vicinity of such sites.

Crops not only reduce leaching rates due to evaporation, they also can reduce emission of dust which can affect nearby residents. In addition, plants can increase soil health by providing nutrients and organic matter to the rhizosphere.

2.3 Soil erosion

According to the European Environment Agency⁴:

- Some 42 million ha. of land were estimated to be affected by wind erosion, of which around 1 million ha. were categorised as being severely affected.
- A recent new model of soil erosion by water has estimated the surface area affected in the EU-27 at 130 million ha. Almost 20 % is subjected to soil loss in excess of 10 tonnes/ha/year.
- Increased variations in rainfall pattern and intensity will make soils more susceptible to water erosion, with off-site effects of soil erosion increasing.

Reductions in soil erosion can be achieved by reduced soil tillage, as suggested in conservation agriculture⁵ practices, as well as by the cultivation of perennial crops with dense and deep rooting system. These practices, also applied in the Good Practice cases in Magic, can contribute to protect the soil from erosion and degradation, improve soil quality preserve the natural resources and increase their use efficiency, while optimizing crop yields.

2.4 Dryness

According to the European Environment Agency:

- The largest soil moisture deficits occurred in 2003, 2017 and 2019, affecting over 1.45 million km² in 2019. Soil moisture content was also low in 2012, 2015 and 2018, contributing to increasingly frequent and intense drought pressure.

⁴ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators/soil-erosion-by-water-1/assessment>

⁵ Conservation agriculture, as defined by the United Nations' Food and Agriculture organisation (FAO), is "a farming system that promotes maintenance of a permanent soil cover, minimum soil disturbance, and diversification of plant species. It enhances biodiversity and natural biological processes above and below the ground surface, which contribute to increased water and nutrient use efficiency and to improved and sustained crop production".

Low soil carbon	Soil contamination	Soil erosion	Dryness
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Switchgrass and giant reed in central Greece • Black locust & sunflower in northern Greece • Lavender in Spain • Black locust & Poplar in Germany • Black locust in Hungary • Reed canary grass and Festulolium in Latvia • Willow and miscanthus in Ukraine 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Giant reed in Sardinia • Poplar in Italy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Giant reed in Sardinia • Black locust & sunflower in northern Greece • Lavender in Spain • Black locust & Poplar in Germany • Black locust in Hungary • Reed canary grass and Festulolium in Latvia • Willow and miscanthus in Ukraine 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Switchgrass and giant reed in central Greece • Black locust & sunflower in northern Greece • Rye and Tall wheatgrass in Spain

Figure 2 Good Practices per marginality challenge

The work in Work Package 7 in Magic examined a set of Good Practice cases which include the marginality challenges described in this section. Figure 2 shows the respective Good Practice case studies per marginality challenge in Magic.

3 Industrial crops in the Good Practices of Magic

Most of the industrial crops in the Good Practices in Magic are perennial species. As described in Deliverable 4.1⁶ these crops:

- have low input requirements and their cultivation is associated with very low GHG emissions;
- their cultivation does not require annual ploughing, thus leading to improved soil fertility, carbon sequestration and biodiversity;
- they are stress-tolerant and can be produced under marginal condition.

Table 1 Industrial crops in Good Practice case studies in Magic

Crop	Nature	Type of use
Switchgrass	Perennial	Lignocellulosic
Miscanthus	Perennial	Lignocellulosic
Giant reed	Perennial	Lignocellulosic
Reed canary grass	Perennial	Lignocellulosic
Cardoon	Perennial	Multi- purpose
Black locust	Perennial	Wood
Poplar	Perennial	Wood
Willow	Perennial	Wood
Tall wheatgrass	Perennial	Lignocellulosic
Lavender	Perennial	Aromatic, pharmaceuticals
Festulolium	Annual	Biobased products
Rye	Annual	Food, feed, biobased products

Ten perennial crops have been included in the Good Practice cases analysed in Magic: switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum* L.), miscanthus (*Miscanthus x giganteus*), reed canary grass

⁶ von Cossel, M., Iqbal, Y., Scordia, D., Cosentino, S. L., Elbersen, B., Staritsky, I., van Eupen, M., Mantel, S., Prysiazniuk, O., Maliarenko, O., Lewandowski, I. (2018): Low-input agricultural practices for industrial crops on marginal land (Deliverable D4.1). In: MAGIC project reports, supported by the EU's Horizon 2020 programme under GA No. 727698, University of Hohenheim, Stuttgart (Hohenheim), Germany. <http://magic-h2020.eu/documents-reports/>

(*Phalaris arundinacea* L.) and giant reed (*Arundo donax* L.) are four perennial grasses with good performance in terms of yields, nutrient demand, water use efficiency, adaptability to environmental conditions, etc. Cardoon is a thistle, well adapted to the Mediterranean climate, highly tolerant in drought conditions, with deep rooting system that can protect against soil erosion. Poplar, willow, and black locust are short rotation tree species. Tall wheatgrass and lavender are also perennials with high tolerance in dry, arid conditions, stoniness and slope. All crops have been extensively studied during the last two decades under different agro-ecological conditions and management practices in European regions.

More information for the crop traits is provided below.

Giant reed (*Arundo donax* L.) is a C3 grass, which originates from Asia and is well adapted to European agro-climatic conditions. It is common in the Mediterranean where it occurs wild in marshy areas or by rivers.

The crop is often planted as a windbreak at the edges of cultivated fields, on the banks of dykes etc. and as such helps maintaining soil structure due to its abundant root system. Giant reed has low irrigation and nitrogen requirements, can tolerate severe drought conditions and reported yields range from 5-20 dry t/ha depending on land quality (Christou, 2001; Angelini, 2005; Cosentino, 2006; Angelini, 2009; Nassi, 2010; Cosentino, 2014; Alexopoulou, 2015).

Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*) and miscanthus (*Miscanthus x giganteus*) are C4 warm-season perennial grasses able to produce large amounts of biomass on a wide-range of growing conditions including reclaimed mine lands (Skousen et al., 2013). Switchgrass has spread across central and northern America over time from tropical origins and has resulted to two discrete ecotypes, lowland and upland varieties. Lowland varieties grow better in deep moist soils, while upland varieties tend to be better adapted to thinner soils and drier sites (Elbersen, 2004; Parrish and Fike, 2005, Monti, 2006). Results reported in literature state that the crop is well adapted to the region and exhibits yields of 10- 17.5 t/ha/year (Alexopoulou, 2008; Giannoulis, 2014; Giannoulis, 2016;).

Miscanthus is a warm-season C4 perennial grass native to Asia and Africa (Hecht, 2011). The most widely used miscanthus species for biomass production is *Miscanthus x giganteus*, which is a sterile hybrid (Skousen et al., 2014). The crop shares similar growth characteristics to switchgrass and other warm-season perennial species with growth from rhizomes that reach a maximum height of 3 to 3.5 m (Skousen et al., 2014). It has low nutritional requirements and high nitrogen use efficiency and therefore can grow well on marginal land without heavy fertilization requirements (Lesur, 2013; refs). *M. giganteus* is a sterile hybrid and therefore propagates vegetative underground through its rhizomes (Lewandowski, 2000). The crop is currently used commercially in EU for heat, electricity and lignocellulosic ethanol.

Cardoon (*Cynara cardunculus*)⁷ is a perennial herb which reaches 1.1 to 1.8 m in height under marginal conditions (Wiklund, 1992). It is often richly branched and produces a very deep perennial taproot from which the plant regenerates each year (Kelly & Pepper, 1996). The root crown can also produce multiple plants, serving as a form of asexual reproduction. *C. cardunculus* forms a rosette up to 1 m or more in diameter composed of very large leaves. Leaves are silky greyish-green on the upper surface and appear almost white on the under surface because of the dense mat of white hairs. Leaves are deeply divided, each lobe ending in a strong yellow spine. In spring a tall flowering stem up to 2 m high is produced. One large, fragrant blue or purple flower forms at each branch apex. The flower heads consist of tubular florets surrounded by a series of rigid bracts tipped with spines. Each plant may produce up to 50 heads. Seeds are brown to black, about 5 mm long with a smooth covering. Seeds are wind-dispersed, each with a pappus about 4 cm long.

Poplar is a perennial C3-crop, currently especially planted for pulpwood production in various countries. Current typical rotation times 3-4 for coppice systems or 8–10 years for single stem systems.

⁷ (<http://www.iucngisd.org/gisd/species.php?sc=1696>)

Willow⁸, *Salix alba*, is a fast-growing large tree or shrub, with height from 13.7 to 21 m, and spread ranges within the same limits as its height. *Salix* spp. is native almost to every country in Europe and grows well on moist and well drained soils but, it can tolerate a great range of soils such as wet sites, alkaline, clay soils and road salt. It needs 6 hours of direct sun light and to 6 hours of day light, it has been categorized in hardiness zones 2 to 8. *Salix alba* is moderately tolerant to salt spray and intolerant in drought conditions.

Black locust is native to North American but in Europe it was first introduced in 17th century from Sicily. Now it is wide-spread and introduced species throughout Europe and an alien species. It is also native in Eastern United States and today is cultivated in all 48 states of eastern Canada and British Columbia. Black locust has been introduced to Pakistan, India, Australia, China, Northern and South Africa. It is also considered invasive within the western United States.

Rye has been a traditional cereal crop grown in Europe and known to have high rusticity and good adaptation to colder climatic conditions. The crop is grown primarily in Eastern, Central and Northern Europe. The main rye belt stretches from northern Germany through Poland, Ukraine, Belarus, Lithuania and Latvia into central and northern Russia⁹. It is more tolerant of frost and drought than wheat that is why it has been selected for marginal land.

Tall Wheatgrass - ...
greatbasinseeds.com

Tall wheatgrass (*Agropyron elongatum*)¹⁰ is a tall, coarse, late-maturing bunchgrass. It is native to saline meadows and seashores of south-eastern Europe and Asia Minor. It was introduced into the United States from Turkey. Tall wheatgrass has high tolerant drought and it has been cultivated in rainfed conditions. It is a perennial crop with a high regrowth capacity. It requires spring

⁸ Factsheet on Weeping Willow, Edward F. Gilman and Dennis G. Watso1994 <http://hort.ufl.edu/trees/SALSPPA.pdf>

⁹ en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rye

¹⁰ http://www.soilcropandmore.info/crops/Grasses/Tall_Wheatgrass/Tall-wheatgrass.htm

rainfall (April-June), however, if there is low precipitation in spring It will result in low biomass yields. The crop has also demonstrated its ability to thrive in sub-irrigated, saline soil where foxtail barley is usually the dominant grass. Tall wheatgrass is the latest-maturing grass adapted to the continental climate areas of the west and one of the most productive. is especially tolerant of saline soils. It is adapted to irrigated or sub-irrigated saline soils and to imperfectly drained, alkali soils. It prefers soils with a high-water table. It can survive five weeks of flooding in the spring and can, therefore, be seeded on land that is wet for some time in spring. The ability of this grass to grow and maintain itself on moist, moderately alkaline soils has resulted in its extensive use in reclaiming such areas. It will not develop in dry, alkaline sites, nor will it grow where the soil is so alkaline that native plants or weeds cannot persist. It has been established on soils with a pH as high as 10.1.

Photo source: Lavender field, Dorset, UK, www.alamy.com

Lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia*) is an evergreen, perennial Shrub growing to 1.2 m by 1 m at a slow rate. The leaves are evergreen, 2–6 cm long, and 4–6 mm broad. The flowers are pinkish purple (lavender-colored), pro-duced on spikes 2–8 cm long at the top of slender, leafless stems 10–30 cm long.

Reed canary grass (*Phalaris arundinacea*) is a tall, perennial bunchgrass that commonly forms extensive single-species stands along the margins of lakes and streams and in wet open areas, with a wide distribution in Europe, Asia, northern Africa and North America. It is a cool-season perennial wetland grass that spreads via a dense rhizome system into clumps or colonies.

Festulolium¹¹ is a hybrid cross between the Festuca and Lolium species. The agronomic benefits of festulolium started to gain acceptance in the late 1950's with demand steadily increasing over the years. Festulolium is mainly utilized in pastures for grazing and stockpiling, either in mixes or pure stands. Silage and green chop are other major uses. Benefits include higher forage yields than perennial ryegrass, forage quality similar to perennial

¹¹ <https://www.alliedseed.com/forage/Festulolium/>

ryegrass, increased midsummer growth compared to other cool season grasses, high disease resistance, winterhardiness and persistence.

4 Marginality challenges improved with the cultivation of industrial crops in the Magic Good Practice case studies

The Good Practice case studies in Magic examined a variety of marginality challenges across European regions. The severity of these challenges before the crop cultivation has been ranked by the case study interviewed stakeholders as high, moderate, low (coloured respectively as red, amber and green).

Table 2 Severity of marginality challenges in the Good Practice case study regions

Region	Low soil carbon	Soil contamination	Soil erosion	Dryness
Greece				
Central Greece	Red	White	Yellow	Yellow
East Macedonia/ Thrace	Red	White	Red	Green
Italy				
Catania	Red	White	Yellow	Yellow
Sardinia	Red	Red	White	Red
Central Italy, Lazio	Yellow	Red	Green	Yellow
Spain				
Soria, Castilla y Leon	Red	White	Yellow	Red
Castilla-La Mancha, Cuenca province	Red	White	Green	Yellow
Germany				
Brandenburg	Red	White	Red	White
Hungary				
Észak- Magyarország	Red	White	Yellow	White
Latvia				
Skriveri, Central Latvia	Red	White	Yellow	Red
Ukraine				
Volynska and Lviv (West Ukraine)	Red	White	Red	White
Kyiv Oblast	Red	Yellow	Red	White

Low levels of soil carbon were a significant challenge in all Good Practice cases, except central Italy where it was ranked as moderate.

Soil contamination with the cultivation of industrial crops was a significant challenge in the Italian cases and a moderate one in Ukraine.

Soil erosion was a significant challenge East Macedonia & Thrace in northern Greece, Brandenburg in Germany, Volynska and Lviv in west Ukraine and Kyiv Oblast

Information for the individual marginality challenge profiles of the Good Practice case study regions is provided below.

Table 3 Greece: marginality profiles and industrial crop traits to overcome them

<p>Central Greece </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Abandoned agricultural land ✓ Limiting rooting conditions, shallow soils ✓ Steep slopes 	
<p>Switchgrass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ very well-developed rooting system adaptable to the drought conditions and tolerant to severe water stress conditions ✓ increased potential for carbon storage in soil 	<p>Black locust</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ can grow on a wide variety of soils: although it is sensitive to topsoil compaction and waterlogging, ✓ ability to increase soil carbon
<p>Gaint reed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ perennial, well adapted to mediterranean region ✓ drought resistant with sterile seeds ✓ saline soil tolerant making it suitable for marginal soil conditions 	<p>Sunflower</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ oil crop that can be grown in variety of soil conditions but grows best in well-drained soil with high water-holding capacity ✓ drought tolerant and resistant to salinity ✓ efficient in stratified use of soil resources and has high water use efficiency ✓ grown for phytoextraction of heavy metals like lead and cadmium in contaminated lands

Table 4 Italy: marginality profiles and industrial crop traits to overcome them

<p>Catania</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Soil contamination ✓ Hot summer ✓ Low water availability 	
↓	↓
<p>Giant reed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ perennial, well adapted to mediteranean region ✓ low input crop with high water use efficiency and relevant carbon storage potential. 	
<p>Miscanthus</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Perennial, well adapted to European agro-climatic conditions ✓ does not require a big input of fertilisers due to good nutrient use efficiency 	<p>Cardoon</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ rainfed crop very well in the temperate region with semiarid and sub humid climatic conditions. ✓ low nutrient input
<p>Switchgrass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ wide range of climatic adaptability and can be propagated by seeds ✓ adaptable to drought conditions and tolerant to severe water stress conditions 	
<p>Central Italy, Lazio</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Contamination ✓ Hot summer- wet winter ✓ Polluted underground water 	
↓	
<p>Poplar</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ rooting ability that makes it suitable for rhizoremediation ✓ tolerance in soil acidity and salinity 	

Table 5 Hungary: marginality profiles and industrial crop traits to overcome them

<p>Észak-Magyarország</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Excessive wetness ✓ Adverse terrain ✓ Low fertility soils
<p>↓</p>
<p>Black locust</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Strong ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen ✓ requires little or no nitrogen fertilization ✓ mature harvesting technologies

Table 6 Spain: marginality profiles and industrial crop traits to overcome them

<p>Soria, Castilla y Leon</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Low fertility, sandy soil ✓ Hot summer 	
<p>↓</p>	<p>↓</p>
<p>Rye</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ good adaptation to poor sandy and saline soils ✓ can tolerate cold climatic conditions ✓ can grow with low water availability 	<p>Lavender</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Can be adapted to low quality soil conditions ✓ Oil content is sensitive to water stress
<p>Tall Wheatgrass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Can grow in saline soils ✓ Can be adapted to water stress ✓ Pest resistant 	

Table 7 Germany: marginality profiles and industrial crop traits to overcome them

<p>Brandenburg</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Adverse rooting ✓ Low soil fertility ✓ Abandoned post-mining sites with anthropogenic substrates
<p>Black locust</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ can grow on a wide variety of soils: although it is sensitive to topsoil compaction and waterlogging, ✓ has high heavy metal and acid tolerance. ✓ can assimilate atmospheric nitrogen into the soil, prevent water formation and leaching of contaminants and promotes soil humus accumulation. ✓ other growth limiting factors include sensitivity to late frost and requirement of adequate phosphorous and potassium supply
<p>Poplar</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ fast-growing tree species native to temperate climate zones, ✓ can be grown in low quality soil and requires a moderate soil pH ✓ can be used to clean contaminated, abandoned land, conserve soil by intensive rooting, humus accumulation and minimal nutrient removal. ✓ it has a low tolerance to heavy metals ✓ may exhibit irreversible vitality loss during strong summer droughts

Table 8 Latvia: marginality profiles and industrial crop traits to overcome them

<p>Skriveri, Central Latvia </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Low quality clay soil ✓ Stoniness ✓ Variable rainfall patterns ✓ Drained mineral soil
<p>↓</p>
<p>Reed canary grass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ suitable to grow in sandy soil ✓ well adapted to low fertilisation input
<p>Festulolium</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ well adapted to Baltic countries ✓ can tolerate soil texture of heavy clay and stones and ✓ can grow with inconsistent soil moisture patterns throughout the year

Table 9 Ukraine: marginality profiles and industrial crop traits to overcome them

<p>Volynska and Lviv (West Ukraine) </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Abandoned agricultural land ✓ Degraded low productive land 	
<p>↓</p>	<p>↓</p>
<p>Willow</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ resistant to pest, frost and diseases ✓ good saline tolerance ✓ can be used for phytoremediation 	<p>Miscanthus</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Perennial, well adapted to European agro-climatic conditions ✓ does not require a big input of fertilisers due to good nutrient use efficiency

4.1 Innovation progress in the Good Practice case studies

This section outlines the most important innovation progress that resulted from the implementation of the Good Practice case studies analysed in Magic.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Successful establishment and efficient agronomic practices, tailored to local agro-ecological conditions, for perennial grasses in marginal land
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Innovative systems of vegetative propagation for Giant reed and Miscanthus. Research and demonstration work on hydro-seeding of switchgrass also showed interesting results for the diffusion of the species in marginal lands and sustainable management of the crop
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Introduce new crop alternatives in marginal agricultural lands thus producing opportunities for farmers.
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Enhance the conservation status of floodplain habitats with improved harvesting invasive black locust biomass for renewable energy purposes.
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Improved land management for post mining sites ✓ New low input cropping to produce raw materials for biobased sectors
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ The agroforestry system has given an opportunity to increase the value of the total production through marketing multiple products from given limited spatial and soil resources.
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Improved agronomic practices for the cultivation of bioenergy crops in marginal land at industrial/ commercial scale.
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5 Transferability

Based on the lessons learnt, this section describes issues that can be transferable to other European regions when they plan the restoration of marginal land and the cultivation of industrial crops as feedstock for biobased sectors. Following it discusses the level of potential transferability per key attribute and development stage.

Transferability in this analysis is defined as the process in which knowledge about soil, land, crops and climate change related marginalities is used in the development of biomass supply value chains for biobased economy in another setting and geographical area.

5.1 Biophysical- environmental

Biophysical and environmental attributes in Magic reflect the condition of the soil and the choice of the industrial crop. These are strongly related to the agro-climatic characteristics of a given region but also to the 'potentially available, model- based' projections for the future climate change related impacts. The knowledge gained through the research for Good Practices in Magic includes lessons that can be transferred to other regions, regardless the region-specific characteristics. These are summarised in Table 12.

Table 10 Lessons learnt and degree of transferability for the biophysical- environmental attributes

Stage	Lessons learnt	Degree of transferability
Initial	Transparency in addressing land use change	Moderate to high. It is related to the prevailing legal and institutional framework of each country and region. The existence of national (or transposed from European) rules and monitoring procedures for land use change are very important.
Drive to maturity	Ensuring low impact practices	High as there are plenty examples and good software/ tools available to improve transfer of knowledge and communication with local businesses. The only challenge is to ensure there are job position in the cluster management body to take this on board.
	Location close to regions with high agricultural activity	Moderate and location related
Mature production	Compliance with certification	Moderate to high. It is related to the prevailing legal and institutional framework of each country and region. The presence of a national certification authority with consistent communication and continuous update of the European norms, certification and standardisation procedures is extremely important.
	Long term commitment of landowners	Moderate and reliant to the prevailing situations in each region sand the commitment, persistence and aspiration of individuals

5.2 Economic

Economic attributes in Magic related to the availability of funds for the uptake of innovations which are essential to the successful establishment of the understudy value chains as well as to the cost effectiveness of the practices applied and the economic profitability of the selected crops. The knowledge gained through the research for Good Practices in Magic includes lessons that can be transferred to other regions, regardless the region-specific characteristics. These are summarised in Table 13.

Table 11 Lessons learnt and degree of transferability for the economic attributes

Stage	Lessons learnt	Degree of transferability
Initial	If financing is only dependent on public funding, then there is a risk of stopping the project at this stage	Low to moderate as public co- funding is subject to change and revisions after certain periods of time so the new ones need to be informed and the process requires continuous attention, adaptation and communication of consistent messages.
Drive to maturity	Start up financing from the industry creates better prospects for the longevity and commercial success of the value chains	Low to moderate as it is strongly reliant to the economic situation and competitiveness of individual countries and regions, investment environment and competition with other regions
Mature production	Proximity to raw material users enables cost effectiveness	Moderate as it is strongly related to the location of the marginal land
	Strong and continuous public and private project fund acquisition.	Moderate as long-term commitment requires economic and political stability, trust from investors and funding bodies as well as good success stories with high replication potential.

5.3 Social

Social attributes in Magic are related to the knowledge and networking capacities of any given region where the development of such value chains will take place. The adoption rate of the land use and crop related innovations will depend on the effectiveness of communication as well as on the proximity and involvement of the research providers that can transfer scientific knowledge and advise on the final configuration, the establishment and operation requirements of the value chains.

The knowledge gained through the research for Good Practices in Magic includes lessons that can be transferred to other regions, regardless the region-specific characteristics. These are summarised in Table 14.

Table 12 Lessons learnt and degree of transferability for the social attributes

Stage	Lessons learnt	Degree of transferability
Initial	Networking is of great importance; focus on bringing together farmers, landowners, researchers and the local community.	Low to moderate. Funding to organise networking activities is critical especially in regions with marginal land EU funds for networking & knowledge transfers can be extremely beneficial
	“Open & participatory” approach that ensures efficient transfer of knowledge for the innovative practices required to cultivate industrial crops in marginal land	Moderate to high. Openness and discussions can be facilitated by research organisations, industries or leading individuals. Still, if farmers are not interested or are reluctant to adopt new crops/ practices this can become a challenge.
Drive to maturity	Facilitate openness and organise field visits during key stages of land restoration and crop productivity	
	Improve skills and competences of farmers and local workers	Moderate to high through the improvement of education programmes and dedicated workshops. The challenge at local level may be securing funds to perform the programmes and ensuring

		that adequate experts exist in their regional academic and research institutions. R&D funding from EU can provide strong assistance in such cases.
Mature production	Establish robust contractual relationships and effective, continuous communication channels between farmers/ land owners and raw material users	Moderate to high. The active involvement of the industrial actors is very important.

6 Conclusions

This report presents the key findings and potential transferability lessons from the analysis of the twelve Good Practices cases across Europe of industrial crops cultivated in land with biophysical marginalities.

Key findings from the analysis of Good Practices include:

- Low levels of soil carbon were a significant challenge in all Good Practice cases, except central Italy where it was ranked as moderate.
- Soil contamination with the cultivation of industrial crops was a significant challenge in the Italian cases and a moderate one in Ukraine.
- Soil erosion was a significant challenge East Macedonia & Thrace in northern Greece, Brandenburg in Germany, Volynska and Lviv in west Ukraine and Kyiv Oblast

The degree of transferability of the knowledge gained from analysing Good Practices of cultivating industrial crops in marginal land can be grouped per their relevance to biophysical/ environmental, economic and social attributes of the crops, the products and the value chains. In detail:

- Biophysical and environmental attributes reflect the condition of the soil and the choice of the industrial crop. These are strongly related to the agro-climatic characteristics of a given region but also to the 'potentially available, model- based' projections for the future climate change related impacts.
- Economic attributes are related to the availability of funds for the uptake of innovations which are essential to the successful establishment of the understudy value chains as well as to the cost effectiveness of the practices applied and the economic profitability of the selected crops.
- Social attributes are related to the knowledge and networking capacities of any given region where the development of such value chains will take place. The adoption rate of the land use and crop related innovations will depend on the effectiveness of communication as well as on the proximity and involvement of the research providers that can transfer scientific knowledge and advise on the final configuration, the establishment and operation requirements of the value chains.